

Deciphering tree drought responses across species: linking leaf water potentials with remote sensing greenness and photoprotection dynamics

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring forest drought stress requires indicators that capture tree water relations across species and scales. Remote sensing enables large-scale assessment of drought vulnerability, but species-specific water and light use strategies complicate data interpretation, underscoring the need for mechanistic insights into remotely sensed signals in mature trees. We investigated drought responses of seven common European tree species (*Abies alba*, *Picea abies*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Quercus* sp.) at a temperate forest throughfall exclusion site during the 2023 peak growing season, integrating drone-based multispectral imagery with measurements of leaf water potential, turgor loss point, and leaf pigments. Our goal was to assess whether drone-derived greenness and photoprotection indicators capture species-specific variation in tree water status and contribute to a mechanistic interpretation of remote sensing signals over seasonal and diurnal timescales. We found that the photochemical reflectance index (PRI) strongly correlated with leaf water potentials, capturing both drought-induced declines and post-rainfall recovery, while the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) mostly detected greening losses in *A. pseudoplatanus*, *F. sylvatica*, *C. betulus*, but failed to reflect recovery. A model combining NDVI-derived greenness and PRI-derived photoprotection accounted for 65–70 % of the variance in leaf water potential dynamics across the site, particularly at midday as a function of species-specific stomatal control. We further found that species experiencing higher stress on their hydraulic system (i.e., lower water potentials) and characterized by lower drought tolerance based on their climatic distributions, generally showed higher engagement of their xanthophyll cycle. This was reflected in higher photoprotection activation rates in the morning (PRI_{rate}) and wider daily operating ranges (PRI_{range}), driven by diffusional and non-diffusional limitations on photosynthesis. By integrating hydraulic and photoprotective functioning, this study highlights both the insights gained and the inherent complexity in explaining interspecific differences in drought vulnerability, underscoring the potential to refine early-warning systems and enable species-specific drought monitoring.

1. Introduction

Numerous recent instances of tree mortality have been associated with atmospheric and soil drought conditions (Hammond et al., 2022). However, our ability to predict spatial mortality patterns over large scales remains relatively weak (Benito Garzón et al., 2018; Hember

et al., 2017; Trugman et al., 2021). A critical gap lies in our limited understanding of species-specific vulnerability patterns during drought, which is essential to predict climate change impacts on biodiverse ecosystems and potential shifts in dominant tree species (Anderegg et al., 2016; Bonan, 2008).

Damage to the hydraulic system of trees due to severe water stress

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has been identified as a key driver of tree mortality during drought (Adams et al., 2017; Arend et al., 2021; Brodrribb and Cochar, 2009; McDowell et al., 2008). One of the main mechanisms by which trees can mediate water loss is stomatal regulation, controlling water potentials (Ψ in MPa) within the plant (Brodrribb et al., 2017). During periods of limited water availability, trees reduce their stomatal opening and thus transpiration to maintain Ψ in a range that maximises plant function and growth while minimizing the risk of hydraulic failure as a consequence of vessel cavitation (Gessler and Zweifel, 2024; Peters et al., 2025, 2023; Sperry, 2000). Predawn leaf water potential ($\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$), primarily reflects soil-root-leaf equilibrium conditions at minimal transpiration and provides thereby an indicator of a species access to soil water and overnight rehydration (Améglio et al., 1999). As evaporative demand and light intensity increase over a day, transpiration peaks around midday leading to minimum leaf water potential ($\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$) (Knipfer et al., 2020). Drought vulnerability, here defined as the exceedance of hydraulic thresholds that induce declines in key physiological processes, has been found varying across tree species (Choat et al., 2018; Dietrich et al., 2019; Kahmen et al., 2022; Leuschner and Meier, 2018). It is therefore fundamental to understand whether Ψ_{leaf} operating ranges primarily represent an adjustment to drought conditions or rather reflect critical threshold exceedance (Anderegg et al., 2016). Among these thresholds, the turgor loss point (or water potential at turgor loss, Ψ_{tlp}) represents the point at which, on average, leaf cells lose turgor, with impacts on cellular structural integrity, metabolism and whole-plant performance (Bartlett et al., 2012a; McDowell, 2011). The ability of a species to maintain its water potential above its Ψ_{tlp} , i.e., a positive hydraulic safety margin (HSM), has been identified as an important predictor of species-specific drought vulnerabilities and drought-induced mortality (Bartlett et al., 2016). However, despite their importance, scaling the monitoring of hydraulic traits across large areas has so far proven unfeasible due to labour-intensive measurement techniques.

Stomatal regulation initiates a cascade of interconnected processes that, in turn, feedback on tree water relations (Zweifel et al., 2007). Among these, leaf shedding has been suggested as a further adjustment in trees to mitigate water loss through the canopy (Chaves et al., 2003; Teskey et al., 2015). Most interestingly, crown defoliation and discoloration can be captured at large spatial scales through remote sensing greenness indicators. Among these, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) has become increasingly utilized over the past decades for studying drought signals linked with vegetation state changes at regional to global scales (Buras et al., 2021; de Jong et al., 2011; Hermann et al., 2023). However, crown vitality assessments within national and international forest monitoring programs have shown that crown defoliation and discoloration often represent lagged responses to severe drought, occurring in the months or years following the stress and representing a drought legacy rather than a real-time drought signal (Bréda et al., 2006; Seidling, 2007). It was further observed that in some species like European beech, drought-induced defoliation starts too late to prevent xylem embolism, suggesting that it might be a consequence of, rather than a protection against, hydraulic failure (Guan et al., 2022; Walthert et al., 2021; Wolfe et al., 2016). Even in species like Scots pine where defoliation has been directly linked to mortality risk (Hunziker et al., 2024), the temporal lag between drought impact and defoliation, complicates causal attribution, as symptoms often arise from the interplay of multiple environmental pressures (Buras et al., 2021; Hermann et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025). This highlights a critical gap of remote sensing greenness indicators primarily reflecting structural vegetation changes (defoliation, discoloration) rather than directly monitoring rapid physiological processes (e.g., stomatal closure, water potential dynamics, embolism).

Remote sensing indicators of tree function, capturing light utilization processes at the level of the photosynthetic system, have the potential to close this gap by providing a real-time assessment of photosynthetic dynamics closely coupled with tree hydraulic functioning. Incomplete utilization of absorbed sunlight is common under full-sun exposure as

light energy often exceeds the maximum rates of photosynthesis (Demmig-Adams and Adams III, 2006). A further usage reduction due to unfavourable drought conditions—where both water deficits and high temperatures impair photosynthetic processes—can lead to excess energy accumulation, triggering oxidative damage to the photosynthetic apparatus and ultimately causing leaf death (Ledford and Niyogi, 2005; Niyogi et al., 2005). Pigment conversion in the xanthophyll cycle prevents this by transforming light energy to thermal energy through a process known as non-photochemical quenching (NPQ) (Demmig-Adams and Adams III, 2006). Pigment conversion in the xanthophyll cycle is a reversible process, that allows the photosynthetic machinery to resume efficient light harvesting for photosynthesis once conditions become favourable again (Demmig et al., 1987; Niyogi, 2000). Xanthophyll cycle activity is tightly coupled with hydraulic functioning. Stomatal closure under drought stress reduces CO_2 diffusion and fixation, causing reduced utilization of absorbed light for photochemistry and thus promoting activation of NPQ via the xanthophyll cycle (Demmig-Adams and Adams, 1996; Galmés et al., 2007; Ishida et al., 2014). Most interestingly, xanthophyll cycle mediated photoprotection is associated with reflectance changes that can be captured through remote sensing and therefore scaled over large areas.

The remotely sensed Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI) compares the xanthophyll pigments induced reflectance change at 531 nm to an independent reference band (typically ~ 570 nm), thus correlating with plants' light use efficiencies (LUE) and state of the xanthophyll-cycle (Gamon et al., 1992, 1997; Garbulsky et al., 2011; Peñuelas et al., 1995). Research on PRI in multi-species systems has been primarily based on experiments with potted seedlings (Hmimina et al., 2014; Peguero-Pina et al., 2008; Ripullone et al., 2011; Sancho-Knapik et al., 2018). However, these studies fail to capture the interspecies differences in drought stress experienced under natural field conditions. Consequently, investigations on mature field-grown trees remain rare and generally either rely on coarse-resolution (1 km) MODIS satellite data, lacking tree-level resolution (Goerner et al., 2009; He et al., 2016; Hwang et al., 2017; Moreno et al., 2012) or do not directly assess tree water relations (Wang et al., 2024a). Further, comparing PRI across species is challenging for at least two reasons: (i) it is influenced by both, rapid xanthophyll-mediated photoprotection dynamics and seasonal variations in pigment pool sizes (Filella et al., 2009), and (ii) while responding to water availability and stomatal regulation, PRI-derived photoprotection dynamics are primarily driven by light and species-specific acclimation to it.

Taking advantage of the Swiss Canopy Crane II experimental research site (SCCII), i.e., a mature temperate forest site with throughfall exclusion shelters that manipulate soil water availability located in the Jura region near Basel, Switzerland, and the natural environmental fluctuations during the 2023 peak growing season, we studied drought responses of seven common European temperate tree species. Specifically, we combined datasets from repeated drone-based remotely sensed multispectral imaging with measurements of leaf water potentials and pigments to achieve two objectives. **Firstly**, assess the ability of a framework that relies exclusively on scalable remotely sensed indicators to assess species-specific tree water relations at a mixed forest research site, including drought and recovery phases. We hypothesize that effectively capturing drought stress responses across contrasting species requires a combination of vegetation state (NDVI), function (PRI), and structural indicators (height, crown size). **Secondly**, we aimed to examine how, under low water availability, species-specific diurnal dynamics of the xanthophyll cycle—captured by PRI light response curves—correlate with species water status at our site and their expected drought tolerances. We hypothesize that species with lower drought tolerance and experiencing higher drought stress, exhibit a higher engagement of the photoprotective system due to higher light dissipation requirements.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Site and experimental design

This research was conducted in a mature temperate forest located on a typical plateau of the Jura Mountains in Hölstein, Basel, Switzerland (47.4386° N, 7.7756° E; 550 m a.s.l., research site of the Swiss Canopy Crane II project; SCCII site (Kahmen et al., 2022)). The mean annual temperature at the site is 9 °C and the mean annual precipitation is 1009 mm. The site has a sparsely rooted shallow silt loam on limestone with an organic layer of 20 cm and a clay fraction of up to 40 %. Since groundwater is very deep on the plateaus of the Jura Mountains, trees depend on local precipitation input into the soil to meet their water demands (Kahmen et al., 2022). Since 2023, a rain exclusion experiment has been running with seven mobile roofs excluding 50 % of the throughfall precipitation during the vegetation period (April – October). The seven roof-covered plots (henceforth „treatment plots”) were installed adjacent to seven plots that were not covered by roofs (henceforth „control plots”) (Figs. 1a, 2).

In 2023, the site included 458 trees from 14 different species with a

DBH > 10 cm and a height of up to 32 m within an area of 1.68 ha. For this study, we focused on seven common temperate tree species that differ in leaf habit, wood anatomy and water use strategy. We included three evergreen conifers, typically characterized by stricter stomatal control, i.e., *Abies alba*, *Picea abies*, and *Pinus sylvestris* (Bachofen et al., 2020; Leo et al., 2014) and three diffuse-porous deciduous species, ranging from more isohydric (*Acer pseudoplatanus*) to more anisohydric (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Carpinus betulus*) stomatal control (Leuschner et al., 2019; Steger et al., 2024; Zapater et al., 2013). Additionally, we included oak (*Quercus* sp.), a ring-porous deciduous species known for its more anisohydric water-use strategy (Epron and Dreyer, 1993; Frank and Thomas, 2000), including sessile oak (*Q. petraea*) and pedunculate oak (*Q. robur*) in various hybrid forms treated here as one species. Species were selected having ≥ 3 replicate trees reaching the dominant canopy layer, for both control and treatment plots. This resulted in 69 target trees (Fig. 1a) sampled using a 50-m tall canopy crane with a 62.5 m jib installed in the centre of the site. Additional 146 trees, unevenly distributed among species and treatment groups, were available for drone-based screening but were lacking paired ground measurements (Fig. S1). Paired leaf water potential measurements and drone-based

Fig. 1. Throughfall exclusion forest research site in Hölstein, Basel, Switzerland (47.4386° N, 7.7756° E; 550 m a.s.l.; site of the Swiss Canopy Crane II; SCCII). (a) The experimental design distinguishing control and treatment (roofs) plots, including tree species distribution and crane position; (b) Canopy Height Model (CHM) from drone-based LiDAR acquisitions; (c) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and (d) Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI) maps from drone-based multispectral imagery acquired on 22. August 2023.

Fig. 2. Environmental parameters at the SCCII site over the measurement year 2023: (a) daily mean air temperature (T_a) and daily maximum vapor pressure deficit (VPD), (b) daily sums of rainfall and Daily Light Integral (DLI), and daily mean soil water potential (Ψ_{soil}) at (c) 10 cm and (d) 40 cm depth averaged over control and treatment plots with shaded areas representing standard deviations. Dashed vertical lines indicate dates of the drone flights. Top: pictures of crane for canopy sampling, throughfall exclusion shelters and trenches at the site.

crown imaging were obtained for four dates over the peak growing seasons: 7 July, 31 July, 22 August and 2 September 2023. Samples for leaf/needle pigments were collected on 31 July and 22 August 2023.

2.2. Environmental measurements

To contextualize the 2023 drought event within the long-term local climate, we analysed weather data from the nearby MeteoSwiss climate station in Rünenberg. This station is located about 10 km to the east of our SCCII site (47.4346° N, 7.8794° E), at an elevation of 612 m a.s.l.. We computed growing season averages (April–September) for air temperature and precipitation, then derived their annual anomalies relative to the 1991 - 2020 reference period.

Local air temperature (T_a in °C), relative humidity (RH in %), photosynthetic active radiation (PAR in $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), and precipitation (mm) at the SCCII site were monitored using a weather station (Davis Vantage Pro 2; Scientific Sales Inc., Lawrenceville, NJ, USA) at 10-min intervals. T_a and RH were used to calculate vapour pressure deficit (VPD in kPa) (Fig. 2a, b). Additionally, Ψ_{soil} (kPa) was measured (MPS-2; Decagon Devices, Pullman, WA, USA) at a soil depth of 10 and 40 cm, with Ψ_{soil} measurement pits located to capture the diversity of the site. To represent the Ψ_{soil} dynamics in treatment and control plots, we averaged the values measured from all sensors for the two groups.

2.3. Leaf water potentials & turgor loss points

Ψ_{leaf} was measured with a Scholander-type pressure chamber (Model 1000; PMS Instruments, Albany, OR, USA) on c. 10-cm-long terminal shoots collected using the canopy crane from trees' upper part of sunlit canopies with three to four leaves (for broadleaves species) or 3 to 5 years shoots (for conifer species). Ψ_{leaf} of all 69 target trees was measured at the beginning of July, end of July, middle of August and beginning of September 2023. Each measurement campaign spanned two days, either consecutive or 1–2 days apart but with comparable environmental conditions. During each campaign measurements were conducted predawn (~5:00 Central European Time; CET) and close to midday.

To relate Ψ_{leaf} operating ranges to species-specific hydraulic thresholds we determined the turgor loss points of each species (Ψ_{tlp}), defined as the Ψ_{leaf} at which, on average, leaf cells lose turgor and the leaf wilts (Bartlett et al. 2012a). On the same dates of Ψ_{leaf} measurements within the peak growing season, 5–10 cm long branches were collected from all target trees, stored in cooling boxes and transported to the lab. Upon arrival, each branch was recut underwater and rehydrated for several hours by submerging the xylem, ensuring complete rehydration by confirming that Ψ_{leaf} exceeded -0.5 MPa (Arndt et al., 2015). Once fully hydrated, fully developed leaves or needles were collected,

and the leaf material was placed in 1.5 ml micro-tubes and frozen overnight at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to fracture membranes and cell walls. After freezing, the 1.5 ml micro-tubes were punctured with a needle and placed inside 2 ml micro-tubes for sap extraction via centrifugation. The osmolality of the sap was measured using the OSMOMAT 3000 device (Gonotech, Berlin, Germany) and expressed as molar concentrations of solutes per mass of water (mol kg^{-1}). The Ψ_{tip} was determined following the method described by Sjöman et al. (2015), based on the relationship with osmotic potential at full rehydration described in Bartlett et al. (2012a,b). Hydraulic safety margins (HSM) were then calculated as the difference between species-specific Ψ_{tip} and Ψ_{leaf} at predawn and midday on a specific date.

2.4. Photosynthetic pigments

Leaf and needle samples were collected from the sun-exposed canopy of all 69 target trees during two measurement campaigns (31 July 2023 at predawn and midday; 22 August 2023 at midday). Samples were stored on dry ice in the field, then freeze-dried, ground, and extracted in a H_2O :acetone solution. Pigment analysis was performed using ultrahigh-performance liquid chromatography with photodiode array detection (UHPLC-PDA). Pigments were identified based on retention times and quantified using calibration curves from reference standards. Detailed extraction and chromatographic procedures are provided in the Supplementary Material.

The de-epoxidation state (DEPS) of xanthophyll cycle pigments was calculated according to Thayer and Björkman (1990) as:

$$\text{DEPS} = (0.5A + Z)/(V + A + Z) \quad (1)$$

where antheraxanthin (A), zeaxanthin (Z) and violaxanthin (V) are the xanthophyll cycle pigments. Higher DEPS values indicate a greater conversion of V to A and Z, reflecting increased engagement of the xanthophyll cycle in photoprotection under high light stress conditions. Total Chlorophylls (Chl) included Chl a and b, while total carotenoids (Car) included V, A, Z, neoxanthin, lutein and beta-carotene.

2.5. Drone-based indicators

2.5.1. NDVI and PRI

Narrow-band multispectral imagery (Table S1) was collected using a multispectral camera (Micasense Dual; Micasense, Seattle, WA) mounted on a quadcopter drone (DJI Matrice 300 RTK UAV; DJI Technology Co., Ltd., Shenzhen, China). Drone flights were conducted under sunny, clear sky conditions on the four dates between beginning of July and beginning of September 2023 coinciding with the water potentials measurement campaigns. Midday acquisitions were typically performed within 2 h of local solar noon to minimize shadows. On 22 August, corresponding to the measurement campaign within the drought period, diurnal flights were performed at c. 08:00, 12:00, 15:00 and 18:00 CET.

Drone image processing to obtain orthomosaics as well as digital surface models (DSMs) and digital terrain models (DTMs), was performed using the commercial Agisoft Metashape software (Agisoft LLC, St. Petersburg, Russia, 191,144). Irradiance data recorded during flight by the Downwelling Light Sensor (DLS) in the same ten bands as the down-looking sensors, were used to inspect the stability of illumination conditions during each flight. A grey 60 % reflective panel imaged before and after each flight was used for reflectance calibration. Ground sampling distance was between 5 and 7 cm/pixel and orthomosaics were co-registered to RGB RTK-tagged images resulting in 2–5 cm horizontal and 5–10 cm vertical geolocation accuracy. In ArcGIS Pro (version 3.1, Esri, Redlands, CA, USA) the canopy height model (CHM), obtained as the difference between the DSM and the DTM, was used to mask out pixels belonging to ground and understory vegetation applying a threshold of 5 m. Finally, tree crowns were assigned and delineated through visual interpretation and expert knowledge. For midday

acquisitions, a binary shade mask, obtained from the bimodal distribution classification of the respective near-infrared (NIR) band at 842 nm, was used to exclude shaded pixels, while they were included in the diurnal analysis (for details on the method see (D'Odorico et al., 2021)). This distinction reflects differing objectives: the midday analysis examines PRI variations driven by seasonal water status under consistent illumination, while the diurnal analysis focuses on PRI changes in response to increasing irradiance under drought conditions.

Two indices were computed from the multispectral dataset. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Tucker, 1979), leveraging the red band's sensitivity to chlorophyll absorption at 668 nm and the near-infrared band's sensitivity to leaf/canopy structure at 842 nm, was computed as:

$$\text{NDVI} = (R_{842\text{nm}} - R_{668\text{nm}})/(R_{842\text{nm}} + R_{668\text{nm}}) \quad (2)$$

with higher NDVI values typically indicating higher greening resulting from higher Leaf Area Index (LAI) and chlorophyll content, while lower values suggest higher crown defoliation and discoloration.

The photochemical reflectance index (PRI) (Gamon et al., 1992), exploiting the narrow green band's sensitivity to the de-epoxidation of xanthophyll pigments at 531 nm and the insensitivity to changes in the xanthophyll cycle of the reference green band at 560 nm (various reference bands have been proposed, see (Hernández-Clemente et al., 2011)), was computed as:

$$\text{PRI} = (R_{531\text{nm}} - R_{560\text{nm}})/(R_{531\text{nm}} + R_{560\text{nm}}) \quad (3)$$

with lower values suggesting increased xanthophyll cycle mediated photoprotection (higher DEPS) and lower photosynthetic light use efficiency (LUE). Finally, tree level NDVI and PRI values were obtained by averaging pixels within manually delineated crown polygons, for which shade (except for diurnal) pixels had been removed.

2.5.2. PAR albedo

A proxy for the absorbed light by tree crowns was obtained following the method proposed by Gamon et al. (2023), and used to build diurnal PRI light response curves. In general, a higher PAR albedo means a potentially higher fraction of this absorbed light deviated from photochemistry to NPQ pathways (i.e., higher DEPS and lower PRI). Tree crown spectral albedo was estimated by integrating the measured surface reflectance in the PAR range (400–700 nm) from the 10-band spectra (Table S1) for each pixel, yielding an apparent PAR albedo. Gamon et al. (2023) found a strong linear relationship between irradiance and PAR albedo ($R^2 = 0.78$ –1 for different illumination scenarios and canopy reflectance values) supporting the use of PAR albedo as a pixel-level irradiance proxy (for details on the method see (Gamon et al., 2023)).

2.5.3. Crown area and tree height

Crown area, a surrogate for tree photosynthetic biomass, was obtained by calculating the area seen from a bird-eye perspective and delimited by the crown polygons superimposed on the multispectral orthomosaic. Tree heights were obtained from a Canopy Height Model (CHM) to reflect differences in hydrostatic gradients, with taller trees typically experiencing more negative water potentials at canopy level due to gravitational effects. The CHM was obtained from LiDAR (Light detection and ranging) data acquired on 27 July 2023 with a miniVUX-3 UAV Scanner (Riegl) mounted on a hexacopter drone (DJI Matrice 600).

2.6. Statistical analysis

2.6.1. Peak growing-season analysis

To assess our first objective—evaluating a framework based solely on scalable remote sensing indicators for explaining tree water relations—we analysed how PRI and NDVI varied with changes in pre-dawn and midday Ψ_{leaf} during two key transitions: from pre-drought to

drought (31 July – 22 August) and from drought to recovery (22 August – 02 September).

We then compared linear mixed effects models (LMMs) based on remote sensing indicators to explain Ψ_{leaf} measured at predawn and at midday using the lme4 package (v1.1.35.5; (Bates et al., 2015)). The global model included PRI, NDVI, species and their two-ways interactions, as well as tree height and crown area as fixed effects. Tree identity was modelled as a random intercept while date was included as a random slope into the model, accounting for the fact that temperature or other environmental parameters could influence the relationship. Automated backward model selection was conducted using the R dredge function from the MuMIn package (v1.48.4; (Bartoń, 2024)), testing all fixed predictor combinations starting from the global model. Homoscedasticity and normality of residuals were verified graphically to check for model violations. All models fitted by maximum likelihood were then compared based on the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to obtain the best model explaining the variability in the data (see summary of models in Table S2–3). The corrected AIC was used as it provides a more accurate model comparison by penalizing models with more parameters when the sample size is limited. The following model was selected:

$$\Psi_{\text{leaf}} \sim \text{NDVI} \times \text{species} + \text{PRI} \times \text{species} + \text{NDVI} \times \text{PRI} + \text{height} + (1 + \text{date} | \text{TreeID}) \quad (4)$$

The model was refitted by the restricted maximum likelihood method and used to investigate estimates, directions and significances of effects on predawn and midday Ψ_{leaf} . All numerical predictors were standardized to be on comparable scales; while sum contrast was used in R for the categorical predictor *species*, as the main rather than marginal effects of *species* were of interest in this study.

Lastly, the variance explained by the model and the relative contribution of each explanatory variable were calculated using the R package lmerTest (Kuznetsova et al., 2017), which provides an estimation of marginal (fixed effects) and conditional (fixed effects and random effects) R^2 values. Similarly, the relative contribution of each fixed effect on the total variance (η^2) was calculated as the ratio of each fixed effect sum of squares divided by the total sum of squares, which were obtained together with significance values based on Type III (Conditional) ANOVA with the Satterthwaite method.

2.6.2. Diurnal analysis

To compare PRI diurnal photoprotection dynamics across species and functional types (second objective), we focused our analysis on data collected on 22 August, the hottest summer day of a drought period at the study site. Species-specific diurnal PRI light response curves were obtained through drone flights conducted between 8 and 18 hrs. To model the relationship between light and PRI and derive metrics for comparison among species, we fitted two models. A linear model of the type:

$$\text{PRI}_{\text{lin}} = a_1 \cdot \text{PAR}_{\text{albedo}} + b_1, \quad \text{for } 0 < \text{PAR}_{\text{albedo}} < 0.01 \quad (5)$$

and a logarithmic model of the type:

$$\text{PRI}_{\text{log}} = a_2 \cdot \log(b_2 \cdot \text{PAR}_{\text{albedo}} + c_2), \quad \text{for } 0 < \text{PAR}_{\text{albedo}} < 0.08 \quad (6)$$

the logarithmic model was chosen based on AIC, R^2 and RMSE statistics

from a selection of models including also rational, power and exponential type functions (results not shown). From these models we extracted the following metrics per species:

- (i) the intercept of the linear model at zero light absorption (b_1 in Eq. (5)), a proxy for species-specific pigment pool sizes (constitutive effects) unaffected by NPQ,
- (ii) the slope of the log model (b_2 in Eq. (6)), hereafter referred to as PRI_{rate} , a proxy for the rate of activation of the photoprotective response with increasing light levels, and
- (iii) the normalized amplitude of PRI over the day ($\text{PRI}_{\text{range}} = (|\text{PRI}_{\text{PAR}0.05} - b_1|)/b_1$), hereafter referred to as $\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$, a proxy for the xanthophyll cycle operating range. PRI at PAR albedo value of 0.05 was selected as it represents the maximum value attained by all species on that day.

Uncertainties associated with these metrics were estimated through a leave-one-out approach. The diurnal analysis was performed at the species level, i.e., pooling treatment and control trees, as neither treatment nor its interaction with PAR had a significant effect on the PRI response (Fig. S2).

3. Results

3.1. Environmental parameters

In 2023, the SCCII site experienced a growing season (April to September) temperature anomaly of + 2.28 °C relative to the 1991 - 2020 reference period, and had 33.32 % less precipitation than average, contributing to exceptionally warm and dry growing conditions.

The four time points of paired Ψ_{leaf} and drone campaigns differed in environmental conditions. Most importantly, our 3rd campaign centred on 22 August, coincided with a hot drought, with the warmest days of the year (avg. $T_a = 26.7$ °C, max $T_a = 34.8$ °C; Fig. 2a), high max VPD (3.04 kPa; Fig. 2a), absence of precipitation in the preceding week (Fig. 2b) and lowest Ψ_{soil} at 10 and 40 cm depth (D) for averaged control (−0.84 MPa at 40 cm D) and treatment (−1.07 MPa at 40 cm D) plots (Fig. 2c,d).

An intermittent rain event (total precipitation 44.9 mm) between 24 August and 1 September, the day before our 4th and last campaign (2 September), led to a release in soil drought conditions with Ψ_{soil} increasing in both control (−0.62 MPa at 40 cm D) and treatment (−0.78 MPa at 40 cm D) plots to pre-drought levels (Fig. 2c, d).

3.2. Dynamics of water potentials, PRI and NDVI during drought and recovery

The impact of drought on water potentials and remotely sensed indicators across different species and treatments was analyzed between 31 July (pre-drought) and 22 August (drought), capturing the transition into drought. This phase was characterized by a decline in water potentials, PRI and NDVI values across species, with a more pronounced decline in treatment trees (however, mostly non-significant with $p > 0.05$; Fig. 3, Table 1).

PRI closely tracked tree ($\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$) and soil (Ψ_{soil} ; Fig. 2c) water potentials, evidencing significantly lower values (i.e., higher excess energy

Fig. 3. Dynamics of leaf water potentials and drone-based crown-level spectral indicators for treatment (filled markers) and control (empty markers) trees at the SCCII site over summer 2023. Water potentials were measured at predawn (Ψ_{leaf_pd} ; a-g) and at midday (Ψ_{leaf_md} ; h-n), with red dashed lines representing species-specific turgor loss points. Spectral indicators include midday photochemical reflectance index (PRI; o-u) and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI; v-bb). Top: species and number of trees are reported as (treatment | control). Significant differences between control and treatment trees for each date are indicated by asterisks ($p < .1$, $*p < .05$, $**p < .01$, $***p < .001$). For all parameters, lower values indicate higher stress levels.

Table 1

Statistical significance of changes in leaf water potentials and drone remote sensing indicators during drought and recovery periods for different species and treatments. P-values were obtained using independent *t*-tests comparing values between July 31 and August 22 (drought response) and between August 22 and September 2 (recovery response). Number of target trees for control (C) and treatment (T) are reported in brackets.

	<i>A. alba</i>		<i>P. abies</i>		<i>P. sylvestris</i>		<i>A. pseudo-platanus</i>		<i>F. sylvatica</i>		<i>C. betulus</i>		<i>Quercus sp.</i>	
	C (3)	T (4)	C (6)	T (6)	C (6)	T (6)	C (4)	T (3)	C (6)	T (6)	C (3)	T (4)	C (6)	T (6)
Drought response														
Ψ_{leaf_pd}	0.030	<i>0.087</i>	<0.001	<i>0.093</i>	0.002	0.013	0.009	<0.001	<0.001	0.001	0.002	0.250	<0.001	0.113
Ψ_{leaf_md}	0.670	0.938	0.794	0.186	0.383	1.000	<i>0.085</i>	<0.001	0.010	0.035	0.032	0.225	0.004	<i>0.092</i>
PRI	0.991	0.138	<i>0.056</i>	0.012	<i>0.077</i>	0.026	0.248	<i>0.088</i>	0.022	0.049	0.357	0.421	0.046	<i>0.080</i>
NDVI	0.209	0.756	0.155	0.112	0.022	<i>0.051</i>	0.229	<i>0.051</i>	0.016	0.144	0.011	0.116	0.973	0.222
Recovery response														
Ψ_{leaf_pd}	0.032	0.794	<0.001	0.003	<0.001	0.005	0.010	<0.001	<0.001	0.000	0.001	0.207	<0.001	<i>0.097</i>
Ψ_{leaf_md}	0.588	0.737	0.305	0.008	0.127	0.023	0.030	<0.001	0.007	0.030	0.014	0.167	0.004	0.194
PRI	0.163	0.149	0.008	<0.001	0.004	<0.001	0.588	0.006	0.023	0.025	0.022	0.011	0.010	0.394
NDVI	0.840	0.999	0.457	0.773	0.499	0.329	0.635	0.812	0.542	0.661	0.806	0.886	0.431	0.964

Ψ_{leaf_pd} : predawn leaf water potential; Ψ_{leaf_md} : midday leaf water potential; PRI: Photochemical Reflectance Index; NDVI: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index. Significant effects ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold, marginally significant effects ($p < 0.1$).

dissipation) on 22 August as compared to 31 July for all species and both treatments, except for *A. alba* and *C. betulus* (Table 1, Fig. 3o-u). NDVI revealed a significant decline in greenness during the drought event for *A. pseudo-platanus* (treatment), *F. sylvatica* (control), and *C. betulus* (control) among broadleaf species (Table 1, Fig. 3v-bb). In contrast, *Quercus sp.* showed no evidence of drought impact on greenness. Among conifers, only *P. sylvestris* exhibited significant NDVI differences between drought and pre-drought conditions.

The impact of recovery, following an intermittent rain event that replenished soil water reserves in both control and treatment plots

(Fig. 2b-c), was analysed between 22 August (drought) and 2 September (post-drought). This phase saw a functional recovery for all drought impacted species evidenced by water potentials closer to zero and higher PRI values (i.e., higher photosynthetic LUE). In contrast, NDVI did not recover to pre-drought levels (Table 1, Fig. 3v-bb).

3.3. Leaf water potentials captured by remotely sensed indicators of greenness and photoprotection

A linear mixed-effects model (Eq. (4)), including PRI, NDVI, tree

Table 2

Linear mixed effect model results of the effects of species, tree height, drone-based spectral indicators of vegetation state (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, NDVI) and function (Photochemical Reflectance Index, PRI) and their two-way interactions, on tree water relations: predawn leaf water potential ($\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$) and midday leaf water potential ($\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$).

Explained variables	R^2 $R^2_{\text{fixed}} (R^2_{\text{total}})$	Explanatory variables						
		Species p value (η^2)	Height p value (η^2)	NDVI p value (η^2)	PRI p value (η^2)	NDVI \times PRI p value (η^2)	Species \times PRI p value (η^2)	Species \times NDVI p value (η^2)
$\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$	0.54 (0.65)	0.004 (9)	<0.001 (5.9)	<0.001 (17.9)	<0.001 (45.2)	<0.001 (8.9)	0.04 (6.1)	0.02 (7)
$\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$	0.64 (0.70)	<0.001 (33.9)	<0.001 (8.7)	<0.001 (9.5)	<0.001 (6.5)	<0.001 (17.7)	<0.001 (13.5)	0.001 (10.3)

The R^2 indicates the variance explained by the fixed effects (R^2_{fixed}) and the variance explained by both the fixed and the random effects (R^2_{total}). The contribution of each fixed effect on the total variance is given in brackets (η^2 [%]). Significant effects are based on Type III ANOVA with Satterthwaite's Method.

Fig. 4. Standardized estimates showing the effects of species, tree height, drone-based spectral indicators of vegetation state (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, NDVI) and function (Photochemical Reflectance Index, PRI) and their two-way interactions, on leaf water potentials (a) at predawn ($\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$) and (b) at midday ($\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$), including four dates during 2023 peak growing season at the SCCII site. Significant effects are indicated by asterisks ($p < .1$, $*p < .05$, $**p < .01$, $***p < .001$). Species include: *Abies alba* (Aa), *Picea abies* (Pa), *Pinus sylvestris* (Ps), *Acer pseudoplatanus* (Ap), *Fagus sylvatica* (Fs), *Carpinus betulus* (Cb), *Quercus* sp. (Qs).

height, species, and their two-way interactions, accounted for 65 % of the variance in $\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$ and 70 % in $\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$, with fixed effects alone accounting for 54 % and 64 %, respectively (Table 2). All fixed effects significantly explained variation in Ψ_{leaf} ($p < 0.05$) at predawn and midday conditions. PRI was the most significant predictor of $\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$, explaining nearly half of the total variance ($\eta^2 = 45.2$ %, Table 2). In contrast, for $\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$, species was the strongest predictor ($\eta^2 = 33.9$ %). This was followed by the two-way interactions between NDVI and PRI ($\eta^2 = 17.7$ %), and between species and spectral indicators ($\eta^2 = 10.3$ % and 13.5 % respectively). The importance of species-specific water use strategies in regulating water status under midday conditions is also shown in Fig. 4. Estimates of species effects on $\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$ were higher and more contrasting, with more anisohydric broadleaf species exhibiting significantly lower $\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$ compared to conifers (Fig. 4b). In contrast, species effects on $\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$ were weaker and less consistent across taxa (Fig. 4a). These results suggest that NDVI and PRI effectively capture water status variations, but their relationship with leaf water potential is strongly mediated by species, particularly under midday conditions

(Fig. 4b). Tree height had a significant negative effect on water potentials (Fig. 4a, b), which would likely increase in uneven stands, supporting the role of the hydrostatic gradient in driving lower water potentials in taller trees due to increased gravitational potential and xylem resistance.

3.4. Relationships between drone-based PRI and leaf-level DEPS across species

The relationship between remotely sensed midday crown-level PRI and de-epoxidation state (DEPS) of the xanthophyll cycle was examined, based on leaf/needle samples collected in parallel with drone overpasses on two campaigns — prior (31 July) and during (22 August) the drought period. The decrease in crown PRI captured the increase in leaf-level DEPS and thus the pigment-mediated photoprotection when pooling together all species ($R^2 = 0.35$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 5h). The PRI-DEPS relationship persisted but varied in strength for individual species. Deciduous species, except for *C. betulus*, generally exhibited stronger and

Fig. 5. Species-specific relationships between drone-based crown-level midday Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI) and leaf-level de-epoxidation state of the xanthophyll cycle (DEPS), based on leaf/needle samples taken in proximity of drone overflights on 31 July and 22 August 2023 at the SCCII site (a-h). Dashed lines indicate non-significant trends, while solid lines indicate significant linear relationships ($p < 0.05$). Leaf-level DEPS of species sampled on (i) 31 July predawn, (j) 31 July midday, and (k) 22 August midday, are ranked with significant differences between species ($p < 0.05$) indicated by different letters.

significant relationships between crown- and leaf-level photoprotection status, as compared to evergreen species (Fig. 5a-g).

For all species, DEPS increased from predawn to midday and from pre-drought to drought conditions (Fig. 5i, j, k). However, the extent of NPQ activation varied among species. On 22 August, corresponding to our drought campaign, *Quercus* sp., *A. pseudoplatanus* and *F. sylvatica* exhibited the highest DEPS values (c. 0.63) at midday, while lower but not significantly different values were obtained for *A. alba* and *C. betulus*. In contrast, *P. sylvestris* and *P. abies* exhibited significantly lower DEPS values as compared to deciduous species, except for *C. betulus* (Fig. 5k).

3.5. Diurnal dynamics of PRI and water potentials under drought

PRI light response curves (Fig. 6a-g) were used to derive species-specific metrics of photoprotection rate (PRI_{rate}; Fig. 6h) and operating range (PRI_{range}; Fig. 6i). The decrease in drone-based crown-level PRI with increasing irradiance (i.e., PAR albedo) was effectively captured across all species by the logarithmic model, evidencing a rapid decay during the morning hours and a slow-down during the high-irradiance afternoon (Fig. 6a-g). Target trees (colored markers Fig. 6a-g) generally captured the pattern shown by the extended set of trees (Fig. S1), including those without paired hydraulic traits (grey markers Fig. 6a-g). A slight deviation was observed for *P. abies*, where non-target trees exhibited PRI values at medium PAR albedo that were lower than those predicted by the fitted model (Fig. 6b). PRI_{rate} (Fig. 6h) was highest for *A. alba* and *C. betulus*, followed by *F. sylvatica*, during morning hours (PAR albedo < 0.01). In contrast *P. sylvestris*, *P. abies* and *Quercus* sp. showed the least decline, with *A. pseudoplatanus* exhibiting intermediate values. PRI_{range} (Fig. 6i) was greatest in *A. alba*, *F. sylvatica*, *Quercus* sp. and *C. betulus*. While *A. pseudoplatanus*, *P. abies* and *P. sylvestris* evidenced a significantly narrower operating range over this day (Fig. 6i).

Species-specific PRI metrics were examined in relation to water potentials and their distance to hydraulic thresholds at turgor loss derived for each species at our site (Fig. 7). On 22 August, Ψ_{leaf} and HSM (i.e.,

distances to Ψ_{tlp}) differed among species. *F. sylvatica* and *C. betulus* exhibited the lowest mean Ψ_{leaf} at predawn (−2.5 & −2.4 MPa) and midday (−2.9 & −2.8 MPa), followed by *A. pseudoplatanus* and resulting in negative HSMs at midday (Fig. 7c, g). *Quercus* sp. was the only species exhibiting significant transpiration ($\Delta\Psi_{leaf} > 1$ MPa; Fig. 7h), whereas a $\Delta\Psi_{leaf}$ near zero in all other species indicated minimal or no transpiration during the hot drought on 22 August (Fig. 7h, Fig. S3c). Conifer species at our site exhibited generally less negative Ψ_{leaf} during predawn (> −1.8 MPa) and midday (> −2.1 MPa) conditions thanks to a higher stomatal control during drought, which allowed them to maintain positive HSMs (Fig. 7d, g).

A significant negative correlation was observed between PRI_{rate} and Ψ_{leaf} at predawn ($R^2=0.95$, $p = 0.001$; Fig. 7a) and midday ($R^2=0.73$, $p = 0.03$; Fig. 7e) conditions. This relationship was obtained for a truncated dataset excluding *A. alba*, which was characterized by a high PRI_{rate} despite less negative mean Ψ_{leaf} (−1.5 MPa). A significant negative correlation was also observed between PRI_{range} and Ψ_{leaf} (midday) ($R^2 = 0.92$, $p = 0.002$; Fig. 7f), whereas the correlation with Ψ_{leaf} (predawn) was weaker and non-significant (Fig. 7b). Among the studied species, *Quercus* sp. displayed the widest operating range, in terms of its hydraulic system (i.e., high $\Delta\Psi_{leaf}$, Fig. 7h) and its xanthophyll cycle dynamics (i.e., high PRI_{range}).

3.6. Diurnal dynamics of PRI in relation to known species drought and shade tolerances

Species-specific PRI metrics, obtained on 22 August, with the warmest and driest conditions in our measurement campaigns (Fig. 2), were also examined in relation to drought and shade tolerance rankings proposed by Niinemets and Valladares (2006) (Fig. 8). The latter were obtained from a meta-analysis based on distribution ranges of 806 species representing about 40 % of the existing temperate Northern Hemisphere species pool (for details see (Niinemets and Valladares, 2006).

Drought tolerance as derived by Niinemets and Valladares (2006)

Fig. 6. Diurnal variation in drone-based Photochemical Reflectance Index (PRI) response to photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) albedo at the SCCII precipitation exclusion research site during 22 August 2023 (i.e., drone flight at c. 08:00, 12:00, 15:00 and 18:00 h CET). Coloured points are sample trees with paired physiological measurements, while light grey points are trees without physiological measurements. A logarithmic model is used to fit sample tree observations for each species, goodness of fit is reported as R^2 and RMSE. In (h) PRI_{rate} equivalent to the log model coefficient b , in (i) PRI_{range} calculated as the normalized difference between minimum and maximum PRI (see Methods Section 2.6). Letters indicate significant differences between species ($p < 0.05$).

was negatively correlated with PRI_{rate} ($R^2=0.84, p = 0.011$; Fig. 8a) and with PRI_{range} ($R^2=0.66, p = 0.049$; Fig. 8b), indicating that species associated with lower drought tolerance exhibited a greater activation rate and operating range of photoprotection at our site. This relationship was based on a truncated dataset excluding *P. abies*, which despite being classified by Niinemets and Valladares (2006) as having low drought tolerance showed a low PRI_{rate} and PRI_{range} relatively to other species at our site, in agreement with positive HSM on 22 August (Fig. 7d, g).

A strong positive correlation was found between shade tolerance as derived by Niinemets and PRI_{rate} ($R^2=0.86, p = 0.008$; Fig. 8c) excluding *P. abies*, indicating that species that are more tolerant to shade exhibited a higher rate of photoprotection at our site when exposed to increasing light. The relationship was instead non-significant with PRI_{range} ($R^2=0.45, p = 0.145$; Fig. 8d), indicating that at our site more shade tolerant species only partly resorted to greater photoprotection operating ranges to deal with irradiance over the day.

4. Discussion

4.1. Integrating remotely sensed greenness and photoprotection best tracks leaf water potential dynamics across temperate tree species

The effectiveness of remote sensing indices in tracking changes in tree water relations varied by species and depended on whether trees were entering a drought phase or recovering from it (Fig. 3, Table 1). For most species, PRI revealed a stronger coupling with water relations

compared to NDVI, capturing the peak drought signal emerging from Ψ_{soil} (Fig. 2c) and $\Psi_{leaf\ pd}$ (Fig. 3a-g, Table 2), as well as the post-drought functional recovery of the studied species (Fig. 2b, c). In contrast, NDVI evidenced a decline in greenness only in some individuals of broadleaf species (*A. pseudoplatanus*, *F. sylvatica*, *C. betulus*) and *P. sylvestris*, while it failed to capture functional recovery after the rain event (Fig. 3, Table 2). This is in line with previous studies showing how NDVI fails to detect changes when drought severity remains below the threshold triggering browning and shedding of leaves, with the vegetation state (i.e., greenness) remaining largely unaltered despite impaired vegetation functioning (i.e., downregulation of photosynthetic CO_2 uptake) (Vicca et al., 2016). By contrast, drought can cause trees to shed part of their foliage to decrease water loss through the canopy, without necessarily impairing whole tree functioning which can recover once water availability is restored (Ruehr et al., 2019; Zlobin, 2024). Yet, this will likely translate into an irreversible decrease in greenness in the NDVI signal. Similarly, NDVI has proven to be ineffective in capturing real-time physiological dynamics under conditions of structural overshoot—where excessive canopy buildup from abundant precipitation in the previous years can lead to impaired functioning and thus increased photoprotection requirements (i.e., more negative PRI) during a subsequent dry year (Hermann et al., 2023; Leuschner, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). While NDVI lacks real-time sensitivity to tree physiology and water relations, it captures legacy effects over medium to long time-scales that could become even more significant when considered within a multi-year study. This study, based on one year, already demonstrates

Fig. 7. Relationships between species-specific leaf water potentials and metrics of photoprotection dynamics derived from drone-based PRI light response curves (as presented in Fig. 6a-g) at the SCCII site on 22 August 2023. Species means (\pm std) of leaf water potentials at predawn ($\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$), midday ($\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$) and at turgor loss point (Ψ_{tip}) are plotted against (a, e) PRI rate (as presented in Fig. 6h) and (b, f) PRI range (as presented in Fig. 6i). Species ranking is presented based on (c) absolute $\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$, (d) predawn hydraulic safety margin (HSM_{pd}), (g) midday HSM_{md} , and (h) delta Ψ_{leaf} computed as the difference between predawn and midday values. Solid lines denote significant linear relationships ($p < 0.05$) between Ψ_{leaf} and PRI metrics, dashed lines indicate non-significant trends and dashed circles mark species excluded from regression. Species: *Abies alba* (Aa), *Picea abies* (Pa), *Pinus sylvestris* (Ps), *Acer pseudoplatanus* (Ap), *Fagus sylvatica* (Fs), *Carpinus betulus* (Cb), *Quercus* sp. (Qs).

that a model combining NDVI-derived greenness and PRI-derived photoprotection most accurately captured leaf water potential dynamics across our mixed temperate forest during the peak growing season of 2023 (Table 2, Table S2, S3). As expected, this model based on drone data acquired over midday explained tree water relations more effectively during midday ($R^2_{\text{total}} = 0.70$, $R^2_{\text{fixed}} = 0.64$, Table 2), resulting from species-specific instantaneous physiological responses to environmental stressors (high evaporative demand, stomatal closure), than at predawn ($R^2_{\text{total}} = 0.65$, $R^2_{\text{fixed}} = 0.54$, Table 2; Fig. 4).

Evidence for the combined NDVI and PRI indices tracking tree-level drought stress in temperate mixed forest ecosystems is, to our knowledge, lacking. However, studies in water-limited ecosystems have highlighted the complementarity of these indices as water stress indicators depending on timescale and canopy structure dynamics (Velazquez-Chavez et al., 2024). In Mediterranean olive orchards subjected to varying irrigation regimes, PRI exhibited greater sensitivity than NDVI to diurnal fluctuations in water stress physiology, explaining 70 % of the variation in stem water potential compared with 28 % explained by NDVI (Suárez et al., 2008). A different pattern was observed in a three-year study in a Mediterranean shrubland, where NDVI was more strongly related to drought stress than PRI at seasonal time scales, likely because this ecosystem is characterized by pronounced changes in canopy structure and photosynthetic fluxes associated with seasonal greening (Filella et al., 2004). This aligns with our findings in *A. pseudoplatanus*, *F. sylvatica*, and *C. betulus*, where leaf wilting after midday water potentials crossed their TLP (Fig. 3d-f) was effectively captured by decreasing NDVI values (Fig. 3y-aa; Table 1).

4.2. On the use of PRI light response curves for cross-species comparisons

Comparison of absolute remote sensing index values across species

can be difficult to interpret, as various factors can confound inferences about drought stress. For PRI specifically, normalizations have the potential to reduce the impact of interspecies differences in crown architecture and biochemical composition (e.g., pigment pool sizes), which affect the relationship between PRI and short-term facultative changes in the xanthophyll cycle and NPQ (Barton and North, 2001; D'Odorico et al., 2020; Hernández-Clemente et al., 2011; Wong and Gamon, 2015). To address these confounding effects, several approaches have been proposed. Studies at the leaf-level used PRI of dark-adapted leaves (e.g., measured predawn or following dark-adaptation) to normalize PRI of sunlit leaves and isolate short-term PRI variability (Hmimina et al., 2014; Ripullone et al., 2011). At tree-crown level, recent work by Gamon et al. (2023) presented an innovative approach to exploit spatial patterns of illumination in a single airborne spectroscopy image combined with georeferenced forest inventory data. Following this approach, species-specific PRI-light response curves were used to derive metrics that have the potential to isolate the xanthophyll cycle response (facultative PRI response) from the pigment pool size effects (constitutive response). While Gamon et al. (2023) used a space-for-time substitution exploiting shade-light gradients across a scene, in our study we use a light gradient obtained through drone flights conducted at different times of the day over the same trees under drought. This novel approach leads to PRI light response curves (Fig. 6a-g), that allow the derivation of proxies for the rate of NPQ upregulation (PRI_{rate} , Fig. 6h) and for the xanthophyll cycle operating range ($\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$, Fig. 6i). The rate of NPQ upregulation is inversely proportional to the rate of light use efficiency (LUE) with direct implications for carbon fixation (Kováč et al., 2022; Wong et al., 2020), while the xanthophyll cycle's operating range provides insight into a species' flexibility to acclimate energy utilization across a wide range of light conditions (Demmig-Adams and Adams, 1996). We argue that, particularly for remote sensing indicators

Fig. 8. Relationships between species-specific drought and shade tolerances (higher values indicate higher tolerance) from a meta-analysis study by Niinemets and Valladares 2006 and metrics of photoprotection dynamics (this study) derived from drone-based PRI light response curves (as presented in Fig. 6a-g) at the SCCII site on 22 August 2023. Drought and shade tolerances are plotted against (a, c) PRI rate (as presented in Fig. 6h) and (b, d) PRI range (as presented in Fig. 6i). Solid lines denote significant linear relationships ($p < 0.05$), dashed lines indicate non-significant trends and circles mark species excluded from regression. Species: *Abies alba* (Aa), *Picea abies* (Pa), *Pinus sylvestris* (Ps), *Acer pseudoplatanus* (Ap), *Fagus sylvatica* (Fs), *Carpinus betulus* (Cb), *Quercus* sp. (Qs).

capturing highly dynamic processes like diurnal xanthophyll cycle activity, metrics that describe the kinetics of these processes can offer valuable insights into species-specific strategies for coping with excess light under drought. Moreover, capturing a diurnal gradient allows the separation of constitutive pigment-pool effects from rapid xanthophyll cycle responses, offering improved species-specific normalization and more accurate cross-species comparisons.

4.3. Relationship between species water status and photoprotection dynamics at our site

During the drought campaign centred on 22 August, the range of soil water potentials (-0.7 to -1.23 MPa; Fig. 2c, d), found across plots with and without throughfall exclusion shelters, was representative of severe drought conditions known to limit root water uptake for the studied species (Kahmen et al., 2022; Walthert et al., 2024). Due to the dry conditions in August 2023 at our site (Fig. 1c, d), differences between naturally occurring drought in the control plots and drought treated plots were minimal (Fig. 3, Fig. S2, Fig. S4c). This led to both control and treatment target trees having $\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}} < -1.5$ MPa (Fig. 3a-n; Fig. 7c), often considered indicative of significant physiological impairment (Peters et al., 2025; Wujeska et al., 2013).

On 22 August, a combined assessment of hydraulic and photoprotective functioning revealed distinct water and light use strategies, as well as varying drought sensitivity across species and functional types. With the exception of *A. alba*, we found that species experiencing higher stress on their hydraulic system (i.e., lower water potentials) showed higher engagement of their xanthophyll cycle, with greater activation rates (PRI_{rate}) and operating ranges ($\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$) of photoprotection (Fig. 7a, b, e, f).

Conifer species showed comparatively mild signs of hydraulic stress ($\uparrow\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$, $\uparrow\text{HSM}$; Fig. 7c, d, g), likely due to their tight control of water

loss after stomatal closure (Wang et al., 2024b). In the short term, this water-saving mode allowed them to maintain stable $\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$ and positive hydraulic safety margins by rapidly closing their stomata at midday. However, as shown by Arend et al. (2021) for the 2018 drought—and supported by our continued water potential measurements in autumn 2023—conifers exhibit non-linear declines in water status that can cause the collapse of the hydraulic system within a short time. This pattern was observed in two *A. alba* and one *P. abies* target trees, whose Ψ_{leaf} values dropped sharply in early October (data not shown), pushing trees out of their hydraulic safety zone. This was followed by canopy browning and, ultimately, tree death.

In contrast, photoprotection requirements differed among the three conifers at our site. In *P. sylvestris* and *P. abies*, stomatal-induced CO_2 diffusion limitations did not translate into increased photoprotection, as indicated by low NPQ requirements in the morning ($\downarrow\text{PRI}_{\text{rate}}$; Fig. 6h) and only a modest increase throughout the day ($\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$; Fig. 6i), consistent with low midday DEPS from leaf-level pigment analysis (Fig. 5k). This may be partly explained by the observed negative relationship between PRI_{rate} and leaf mass per area (LMA, Fig. S5a), where evergreen species allocate more carbon to needle structure (Fig. S5b), enhancing structural defence and reducing their reliance on xanthophyll cycle-mediated light dissipation. *A. alba* uniquely deviated from this pattern, as diffusional limitations on photosynthesis may have led to the observed increase in NPQ demands ($\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{rate}}$, $\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$, $\uparrow\text{DEPS}$).

A different pattern emerged in deciduous species *F. sylvatica* and *C. betulus*, which exhibited immediate hydraulic stress ($\downarrow\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$, $\downarrow\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$, $\downarrow\text{HSM}$, Fig. 7c, d, g). This response was likely due to their less stringent stomatal control and constraint to shallow root water uptake (RWU), which restricted nighttime rehydration (Kahmen et al., 2022, 2021; Peters et al., 2023). These species showed high NPQ requirements in the morning ($\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{rate}}$, Fig. 6h) increasing over the day ($\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$, Fig. 6i; $\uparrow\text{DEPS}$, Fig. 5k). We argue that the strong drop in Ψ_{leaf} (partly below

Ψ_{tp}) might lead to strong impacts on the functioning of photosynthetic electron transport and on carboxylation efficiency (Ennahli and Earl, 2005; Flexas et al., 1999). The high engagement of the xanthophyll cycle observed in PRI-based diurnal metrics may therefore indicate non-diffusional limitations on photosynthesis in more anisohydric species. Unlike other deciduous species, *Quercus* sp. showed little to no signs of hydraulic stress ($\uparrow\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$, $\uparrow\text{HSM}$, Fig. 7c, d), maintaining positive hydraulic safety margins even at midday, when less stringent stomatal control allowed water potentials to drop and transpiration to continue ($\uparrow\text{HSM}_{\text{md}}$, Fig. 7g; $\uparrow\Delta\Psi_{\text{leaf}}$, Fig. 7h). The relatively mild signs of stress are also reflected in the low NPQ requirements in the morning ($\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{rate}}$, Fig. 6h) suggesting that *Quercus* sp. maintained a high LUE under low to moderate light levels. However, like in other more anisohydric species, NPQ requirements increased throughout the day ($\uparrow\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$, Fig. 6i; $\uparrow\text{DEPS}$, Fig. 5k), suggesting that non-diffusional limitations may lead to an afternoon depression in photosynthesis, even in the absence of clear hydraulic stress. Lastly, *A. pseudoplatanus* whose leaves are prone to wilting at comparatively high water potentials ($\Psi_{\text{tp}} = -2.1$) was found experiencing signs of hydraulic stress ($\downarrow\Psi_{\text{leaf pd}}$, $\downarrow\Psi_{\text{leaf md}}$, $\downarrow\text{HSM}$, Fig. 7c, d, g), accompanied by intermediate NPQ requirements both in the morning and afternoon (Fig. 6h, i).

4.4. Relationship between expected species drought and shade tolerances and photoprotection dynamics at our site

In addition to evaluating the relationship between species photoprotection dynamics and water status at our site, we also explored their link to expected drought tolerances as reported by Niinemets and Valldares (2006). It is important to note that these drought tolerances are based on species distributions along climatic gradients rather than physiological traits and therefore may reflect drought avoidance more than true tolerance.

With the exception of *P. abies*, we found that species characterized by lower drought tolerance showed higher engagement of their xanthophyll cycle, with greater activation rates (PRI_{rate}) and partly wider operating ranges ($\text{PRI}_{\text{range}}$) of photoprotection (Fig. 8a, b). This suggests that species with distribution ranges extending into drier regions, such as *P. sylvestris*, relied less on xanthophyll cycle quenching than those from wetter habitats when exposed to similar drought conditions at our site (Fig. 8a, b). *P. abies* deviated from this pattern, exhibiting low photoprotection consistent with its positive hydraulic safety margins on 22 August at our site (Fig. 7a-b), yet contrasting with its expected high drought vulnerability, due to its shallow root system and preference for habitats with high and consistent soil moisture (Brinkmann et al., 2019; Stangler et al., 2022). Yet, it should be noted that the extended set of *P. abies* trees (Fig. S1) consisting of individuals without paired water potentials measurements, exhibited more negative PRI values (gray dots in Fig. 6b) than estimated from the model fitted to target trees. This suggests that photoprotection requirements could have been partly underestimated for *P. abies* in our analysis.

Since photoprotection requirements are primarily driven by light before being influenced by soil water availability, we further examined the relationship between species photoprotection dynamics at our site and their expected shade tolerances as reported by Niinemets and Valldares (2006). Shade tolerances were determined based on physiological traits, such as light compensation point, photosynthetic capacity, and growth responses, alongside ecological factors like distribution along light gradients and habitat preferences. We found a strong positive correlation between a species' tolerance of low-light environments and its need to dissipate morning light via NPQ (Fig. 8c). This could contribute to explaining the high photoprotection engagement observed for a highly sciaphilic species like *A. alba* (Fig. 6a, h), despite the positive HSM measured on 22 August at our site (Fig. 7d, h). The ability of a species to acclimate to high light conditions correlates positively with its photosynthetic efficiency and capacity and negatively with its photoprotection potential (Demmig-Adams and Adams, 1996; Yu et al., 2020;

Zhu et al., 2013). Our data reveal contrasting photoprotective responses in *P. abies* and *A. alba*, underscoring the need for further investigation using complementary remote sensing indicators of energy partitioning under drought, such as solar-induced fluorescence (SIF; (Alonso et al., 2017) and proxies of above-ground biomass water content fluctuations such as vegetation optical depth (VOD; (Du et al., 2024; Humphrey and Frankenberg, 2023).

5. Conclusions

A deeper understanding of cross-species response patterns during drought is essential for predicting the sensitivity of trees to drought and tree mortality, the impacts of climate change on biodiverse ecosystems, and shifts in dominant tree species. The challenge of explaining why species differ in their drought sensitivity and vulnerability highlights the need for integrated approaches that extend beyond analysis of isolated mechanisms. Our study demonstrates the effectiveness of a framework that uses remotely sensed indicators of greenness and photoprotection dynamics to assess and scale tree water relations across species, with NDVI reflecting slower structural canopy changes and PRI being more sensitive to rapidly changing photoprotection requirements. Generally, we find support for the hypothesis that species experiencing higher stress on their hydraulic system (i.e., lower water potentials) and characterized by lower drought tolerance mostly show increased engagement of their xanthophyll cycle for photoprotection due to diffusional and non-diffusional limitations on photosynthesis. However, *Abies alba* and *Picea abies* did not always fit these relationships, likely because hydraulic stress and photoprotective responses do not always align during the growing season and are influenced by complementary structural and physiological traits. While our study offers insight into species-specific water and light use strategies, the underlying mechanisms and lasting effects on drought vulnerabilities leading to mortality are not fully understood. Future studies should include complementary traits and be conducted over longer time scales and with higher temporal resolution to better mirror nonlinear trajectories of species-specific responses to drought.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petra D'Odorico: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dominic Fawcett:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Richard Peters:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **David Steger:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Tobias Zhorzel:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Günter Hoch:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **David Basler:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Christian Ginzler:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Michael Eisenring:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Gaétan Glauser:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Roman Zweifel:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Arthur Gessler:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Ansgar Kahmen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.agrformet.2025.110856](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2025.110856).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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